

About Us

Dr.BGR Publications was established in 2015 and now we are one of the researcher's friendly International publisher.

We Support Open Access (OA)

Through OA, researchers can avoid subscription fee and published articles available to the researcher without any financial barrier for download. Dr.BGR Publications is created based on principles of OA.

Our Digital Journals

- ☉ International Journal of Current Science Research (IJCSR)
- ☉ International Journal of Business and Economics Research (IJBER)

IJCSR

About IJCSR

IJCSR is a peer reviewed journal. It is monthly edition journal. IJCSR publishes editorial notes, clinical images, brief report, opinion, book review, obituary, review, and research articles appropriate to the field of science. A minimum of 12 editions are published each year. At 2024, in Volume 10.

Journal Codes

- ☉ e-ISSN: 2454-5422
- ☉ USA: National Library of Medicine (NLM) Unique ID: 101671355

Indexing

Indexed journal is measured to be a superior scientific excellence as compared to non-indexed journal. Our e-journals are indexed in international and national databases such as US NLM Catalog, ROAD, etc.

Impact Factor (IF)

Journal impact factor is regularly used as a pointer of the value of a journal to its field.

- ☉ 2022 - 6.010
- ☉ 2021 - 6.010
- ☉ 2020 - 6.011

- ☞ 2019 - 6.133
- ☞ 2018 - 5.450
- ☞ 2017 - 4.46
- ☞ 2016 - 2.306
- ☞ 2015 - 0.676

Editorial Board

- ☞ Chief Editor
Dr. T. Shanmugaprabha
Assistant Professor of Chemistry
Guru Nanak College (Autonomous), Chennai

- ☞ Deputy Editor-in-Chief
Prof (Dr) Vijay Anant Athavale
Principal
Walchand Institute of Technology
Solapur, Maharashtra

IJBER

About IJBER

IJBER publishes research and review articles on arts. The journal indexed in international ISSN portal. A minimum of 4 issues are published each year. Volume 10 reached at 2024.

Journal Codes

- ☞ e-ISSN: 2455-3921
- ☞ ZDB (German Union Catalogue of Serials) Id: 2899795-5

Impact Factor (IF)

It is commonly used as an indicator of the importance of a journal to its field.

- ☞ 2022 - 6.0120
- ☞ 2021 - 6.0480
- ☞ 2020 - 6.0620
- ☞ 2019 - 6.0740

☎ 2018 - 4.0218

☎ 2017 - 4.147

☎ 2016 - 2.15

Editorial Board

☎ Chief Editor

Dr. T.Selvakumar

Assistant Professor of Economics

The American College, Madurai

☎ Co-Editor in Chief

Dr. S.C.B.Samuel Anbu Selvan

Associate Professor of Commerce

The American College, Madurai

Special Issue

Proposal

Dr.BGR Publications welcome the special issue proposal by guest editor. Special edition contains collection of research / review papers on a specific theme.

Types

☎ Conference / Seminar Papers

☎ Symposium Articles

☎ Workshop Papers

☎ Hands-on training Articles

☎ Specific Theme Papers

Guest Editor

The guest editorial board should be no more than 10 experts, with official information. Subject specialist on a particular topic with a broad network of innovation authors. Commitment to ensure the standard of special issue.

Special Issue Archives

🕒 In-Press

- Two Day International Conference on “Global Contemporary Issues and Unlocking Innovation in Business Industry 4.0” (Hybrid Mode),
Department of Commerce (SF), VHNSNC in association with Department of Business Administration, Mangayarkarasi College of Arts & Science for Women, 24th & 25th July, 2024
Accepted Papers: 93

- International Conference on “Data Economy and Vision India @2047”
Department of Economics,
The American College (Autonomous), 28th & 29th Feb.
Accepted Papers: 45

- 🕒 National Level Conference on The Role of AI in E-Commerce Industry
Department of Commerce,
VHNSNC (Autonomous), Virudhunagar
Published Articles – 44

- 🕒 Proceedings of National Convention of Electronics and Communication Engineers
NCECE-23
Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
Grace College of Engineering, Thoothukudi
Published Articles – 9

- 🕒 Proceeding of National Conference On “Microbial and Biochemical Approach in New Drug Discovery MBAND - 23”
Department of Microbiology and Biochemistry,
Sri Akilandeswari Women’s College, Wandiwash
Published Articles – 52

- 🕒 Special Issue on “Navigating E-Commerce: A Journey Through Its Past, Present and Future (NEJPF - 23)”
Department of Commerce and Commerce C.A,

Sri Akilandeswari Women's College, Wandiwash

Published Articles – 43

- Proceeding of National Conference on Recent Trends in Physical Science Research with A Mathematical Approach RTPRM - 23

Department of Physics, Chemistry & Mathematics,

Sri Akilandeswari Women's College, Wandiwash

Published Articles – 62

- Special Issue On Art of writing articles – A navigation towards research

Department of Management Studies,

Manakula Vinayagar Institute of Technology (MVIT), Puducherry

Published Articles – 16

- Proceeding of National Conference On Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence

NACDAA-23

Department of Computer Science and Applications,

Sri Akilandeswari Women's College, Wandiwash

Published Articles – 112

- 4th National Conference on “Recent Advancements in Civil Engineering (RACE-23)”

Department of Civil Engineering,

Kongunadu College of Engineering and Technology, Trichy

Published Articles – 21

- 8th One Day National Conference on “Challenges and Opportunities for Mechanical Engineers (COME'23)”

Department of Mechanical Engineering,

Kongunadu College of Engineering and Technology, Trichy

Published Articles – 9

- Special Issue: International Conference on “A New Horizon in Materials - INHIM'16

Department of Physics, Sarah Tucker College (Autonomous), Tirunelveli

Published Articles -18

Media Partner

We act not only as media partner but also as publishing partner for your conference.

Benefits we offer to Media Partner

- ☞ Citation your conference in our website
- ☞ Pre-conference advertising through our official page at social media (Fb, etc.)
- ☞ Support the symposium via e-mail marketing
- ☞ Promoting the seminar among the members of our editors

Benefits we expect from the Media Partner

- ☞ Include web link of the Dr.BGR Publications at the conference website.
- ☞ Add our logo and name at brochure

History

- ☞ International Conclave NGS-INDIA 2015, Nagpur University
- ☞ Innovative Teaching and Learning for Sustainable Development in 21st Century, DMI-St.John the Baptist University, Mangochi, Malawi
- ☞ The American College
 - International Conference on Innovations in Business and Management @ 2019
 - International Conference on Sustainability, Transformation Development in Business and Management @ 2020

Membership

Young minds are encouraged to spread good vibrations through their research by Dr. BGR Publications.

Types of Membership

- ☞ Student Membership
- ☞ Faculty Membership
- ☞ Institutional Membership

Benefits of Membership

- ☞ Members will get a digital certificate
- ☞ Free ISBN for books

- ☎ Conference Proceedings @ 250/- per paper

Why Publish with Dr. BGR Publications?

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 - ☞ Number of co-authors
 - ☞ Plagiarism report
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- ☎ Submissions are welcome throughout the year
- ☎ Our Journey Since 2015

Public Connect Events

- ☎ *Webinar*

Venue: Poompuhar College (Autonomous), Melaiyur

Title: International Webinar on “Recent Trends in Biodiversity Conservation and Processing”

Date: 27th Aug. 2020

- ☎ *Practical training*

Topic: Mushroom Cultivation

Venue: VHNSN College

Time: 2019 / Oct. 18

Sponsor: Dr. BGR Publications

- ☎ *Hands on training*

Topic: Mushroom Cultivation

Venue: VHNSN College

Time: 2020 / Feb. 28

Sponsor: Dr. BGR Publications

- ☎ *e-Quiz Jointly with*

Organizer: PMT College

Topic: World Ocean Day 2020

Planner: The American College

Topic: World Population Day 2020

Topic: International Yoga Day 2021

Arranger: Kamaraj College

Topic: World Nature Conservation Day 2020

Organizer: The New Prince Shri Bhavani Arts & Science College

Topic: World Zoonoses Day 2021

On behalf of Dr. BGR Publications

- National Space Day 2024
- International Women's Day 2024
- World Diabetes Day 2023
- Teachers Day Celebration
 - My teacher 2024
 - "ஆசிரியர் 2020"
- World No Tobacco Day Awareness
 - Poster Design Competition: 2023
 - Digital Quiz: 2021
 - Poster Design Competition: 2020
 - Slogan Writing Competition: 2019
- World Thrift Day 2020
- கல்வி வளர்ச்சி தின விழா 2020
- "நாவாய் நாயகன்" 2020
- World Mosquito Day 2020
- National Youth Day 2019

Meet the team

Dr. B.Govindarajan

Founder & CEO

Mrs. J.Ragavi, M.Sc

Proprietor

Mr. M.Arunachalam, B.Tech/IT

Branding Head

Mr. S.Sathananthan, B.Tech/IT

Technical Head

Mr. S.Sakthi N Kumar, B.Pharm

Marketing Head

Mr. P.Senthil Kumar, M.Sc

Indexing Coordinator

Mrs. P.Thirumalaiselvi, B.Sc., B.Ed

Social Media Head

Mr. K.Venkatesh, M.Sc

Finance Head

Mr. R.Venkadesh, B.E/Mech

Creative Head

Books

Books Plans

Respected Human, Publishing a book is an easy task these days. Are you in search of publishing your thesis and books at Friendly Publishing House? You can analyze our ISBN plans and select one that best suits your requirements.

Features	Annual Member	Lifetime Member
Page Limit	70 – 149	70 – 399
Cost of ISBN	Free	Free
Copyright	Always remain with author	Always remain with author
Website Updating	Rs. 499/-	Free
<i>Editing</i>		
Plagiarism report	Add on	Add up
Book Interior Revision	Add on	Single Free Round
Cover Page	Add on	Add up
Proof Reading	Add on	Add up
Digital Proof	Free	Free
<i>Library</i>		
National Library Supply	Add on @ Hard copy	Add up @ Hard copy

Our Books

Title: English Language and Linguistics

Author: Dr. S.Ramanathan & Dr. R.Anandam

FAQ

How many co-authors are allowed in a paper?

There is no limit for co-authors.

What is the pay for extra pages?

Not any. We don't charge extra fees.

Is there any certificate for being a member?

Yes, e-certificate updated at members directory

Which category books I can publish here ?

- Science
- Technology
- Philosophy
- Social Sciences
- Literature
- Arts
- Educational books
- School / Children's books
- Ideology

Costs for obtaining an ISBN from Dr. BGR Publications?

Currently it is free for members. A member gets a single ISBN per year.

Terms and Condition

- Plagiarism action done by "COPYSCAPE".
- No hard copy writing will be mailed.

Welcome to the Team

Dr. BGR Publications

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